

Studies in Terpenes. Part XXX. An Investigation on Wallach's Sylveterpineol Isolation and Elucidation of the Structure of *d-m*-Menthen-6-ol-8*

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The structure of *d-m*-menthen 6-ol-8 isolated from Wallach's sylveterpineol has been elucidated.

By the action of 2% aq. potassium hydroxide on *d*-sylvestrene dihydrochloride (I), Wallach¹ obtained an unsaturated, optically active, tertiary alcohol, C₁₀H₁₇OH, which he designated as sylveterpineol. This alcohol on oxidation² with dilute aq. potassium permanganate gave : (1) a glycerol, C₁₀H₁₇(OH)₃, (2) the δ -lactone of ϵ -keto- γ -hydroxyisopropyl heptonic acid (II) and (3) 2-acetyl-1-methyl- Δ' -cyclopentene (III). The formation of the last two products suggested that the sylveterpineol is in all probability a mixture of *m*-menthen-6-ol-8 (IV) and *m*-menthen-1-ol-8 (V).

More recently, Chabudzinski³ attempted to resolve the components of sylveterpineol through their *p*-nitrobenzoyl esters. Fractional crystallisation afforded two benzoates, (VI) and (VII), m.p. 98° and 66°, which on hydrolyses yielded alcohols (IV) and (V) respectively. These structural assignments were without any valid experimental backing, though it was stated that the higher melting ester corresponded to that originating from naturally occurring sylveterpineol of alleged formula (IV). We report here the study leading to the identification of one of the constituents of sylveterpineol as *m*-menthen-6-ol-8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From *d*-sylvestrene dihydrochloride by agitation with hot 2% aq. potassium hydroxide, we obtained an alcohol fraction, b.p. 90–92°/5 mm. consisting of two components (t.l.c. and g.l.c.) which could not be resolved either by precise fractionation or column chromatography on silica gel. Following essentially the directions of Chabudzinski⁴, the alcohol mixture was esterified with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in pyridine medium. The resulting benzoates, after multicrystallisation, yielded two crops, m.p. 98° and 66° and these upon hydrolyses with hot methanolic potassium hydroxide afforded the corresponding alcohols. When the alcohols were examined by t.l.c. and g.l.c., it was found that only the one derived from the high melting ester was homogeneous. Our interest therefore centred on the higher melting ester, the pure alcohol and the triol derived from the latter.

* A preliminary communication has been published⁴.

1. O. Wallach, *Annalen*, 1907, **357**, 73.
2. W. N. Haworth, W. H. Perkin Jr. and O. Wallach, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 1234.
3. Z. Chabudzinski, *Roczniki Chemii*, 1961, **35**, 985.
4. K. G. Kaimal and J. Verghese, *Current Science*, 1969, **38**, 191.

Structural evaluation : (a) *p*-Nitrobenzoate : Molecular weight and elemental analysis corresponded to the molecular formula $C_{17}H_{21}O_4N$.

The i.r. spectrum (KBr) of the *p*-nitrobenzoate exhibited absorption bands at 1710 cm^{-1} and 1290 cm^{-1} (ester $>C=O$), 1375 cm^{-1} and 1360 cm^{-1} [$(CH_3)_2C<$], 1340 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring) and 1520 cm^{-1} ($-NO_2$ group). The foregoing spectral properties, however, can stem from structures (VI) and (VII) and hence have very little diagnostic value.

The 100 MHz n.m.r. spectra of the *p*-nitrobenzoate were taken both in CCl_4 and C_6D_6 (99% D) in order to take advantage of possible solvent effects.

The spectra showed the following features : AA'XX' system given by the four aromatic protons at δ 8-8.3 in CCl_4 (δ 7.6-7.8 in C_6D_6), olefinic proton at δ 5.34 in CCl_4 (δ 5.39 in C_6D_6), one methyl group on double bond at δ 1.64 in CCl_4 (δ 1.62 in C_6D_6), two tertiary methyl groups on a carbon bearing an oxygen atom at δ 1.60 in CCl_4 (δ 1.44 in C_6D_6) and 7 aliphatic protons in the δ 1-2.4 region in both solvents. Double resonance experiments showed no effect at all on the olefinic proton at δ 5.34 when irradiating the methyl group on the double bond, whereas a sharpening of the resonance was observed upon irradiation of the δ 2.0-2.1 region. For this reason, it was very difficult to decide which structure, (VI) or (VII), is the correct one. On the other hand, the fact that the two tertiary methyl groups give a single resonance line seems to favour structure (VI) where the β -carbon atom is substituted with two methylene groups and not with a methylene and a double bond as in structure (VII). For this alternative structure, one would rather expect different resonances for these methyl groups because of the greater asymmetry of the β -carbon atom. This is only a negative indication though and cannot be taken as evidence.

(b) *Alcohol* : The analytical data of the alcohol corresponded to the formula $C_{10}H_{17}OH$. The i.r. spectrum (neat) of the alcohol had characteristic absorptions at 1667 cm^{-1}

and 820 cm^{-1} ($> \text{C} = \text{CH}-$), 1149 cm^{-1} and 3571 cm^{-1} ($\rightarrow \text{C}-\text{OH}$) and at 1379 cm^{-1} and 1365 cm^{-1} [$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C} <$, doublet]. The above data only revealed the nature of the groups but failed to discriminate between structures (IV) and (V).

The 100 MHz n.m.r. spectra of the alcohol taken in CDCl_3 showed absorption of the olefinic proton on C_6 at $\delta 5.4$. On irradiating at C_1 methyl group at $\delta 1.6$, the broad singlet changed in less broadened triplet, thus indicating that a small coupling with the three methyl protons is eliminated. On irradiating at $\delta 1.84$, we find for the $\text{H}-\text{C}_6$ resonance only a singlet broadened by the former mentioned small coupling. This establishes that the olefinic proton at C_6 is coupled by an allylic coupling with only two neighbours at C_5 as in structure (IV). The absorbances of the other protons in structure (IV) are as described earlier in connection with the n.m.r. spectra of the *p*-nitrobenzoate ester. In the alternate structure (V) for the alcohol, we expect only one allylic coupling of olefinic proton at C_2 with the one at C_3 . Therefore, on irradiating at C_1 methyl group we should get a doublet for the olefinic resonance of this structure. Moreover, the fact that the two tertiary methyl groups give a single resonance line also supports structure (IV) for the alcohol (vide supra).

Clearly then, the above study confirms that the alcohol is represented by formula (IV) viz., *d-m*-menthen-6-ol-8 and the *p*-nitrobenzoate from which the alcohol is released by formula (VI), a conclusion which was indirectly predictable from its n.m.r. spectra.

(c) *Triol*: In order to gain further corroboration of the structure of the alcohol, we subjected the triol (VIII) prepared from the latter to n.m.r. analysis.

The 100 MHz n.m.r. spectra of the triol taken in CDCl_3 displayed for the proton of C_6 , a quartet at $\delta 3.4$ which we must consider as the X part of an ABX system. This shows that the proton at C_6 is coupled with the two adjacent protons at C_5 . The absorptions of the other protons appear between $\delta 2.2$ and 1. The methyl group at C_1 shows a singlet at $\delta 1.64$ while the isopropyl methyl groups give singlets at $\delta 1.26$ and 1.61 .

The isomeric triol (IX), for the resonance of $\text{H}-\text{C}_2$ should show only a doublet.

It was mentioned earlier that the single resonance line for the isopropyl methyl groups is informative in analysing the structure of the *p*-nitrobenzoate and of the alcohol derived therefrom. Likewise, we should expect a single line for the triol also. However, we find a doublet for the isopropyl methyl resonances. At 70° , these lines coalesce to a singlet, thus showing that the splitting is due to the hindered rotation around the C_3-C_4 bond. Thus, the triol is proved to be *m*-menthan-1,6,8-triol (VIII). From this, it follows again that the parent alcohol can only be *m*-menthen-6-ol-8 (IV).

Further studies on the reactions of *m*-menthen-6-ol-8 and on the second component of Wallach's sylveterpineol are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Except where otherwise stated, the following generalisations apply. Melting and boiling points are uncorrected; m.p.s are determined in open capillaries. Pet. ether refers to the fraction, b.p. $40-60^\circ$. Drying of oils is done over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Refractive indices are taken in an Abbe Refractometer (Carl Zeiss, German Model 1665).

Optical rotations are for chloroform solutions. Microanalyses are by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford. Vacuum fractionation is performed in a Todd Precise Fractionation Assembly with a 90 cm \times 1.2 cm. pyrex glass column packed inside with 0.4 cm. pyrex glass helices (column efficiency \sim 60 theoretical plates). T.l.c. is carried out on silica gel G plates (300 μ); solvent system : benzene-methanol (10 : 1); spray : vanillin (5%) in concd. sulphuric acid. G.l.c. is performed either on Column P, 20% polyester (diethylene glycol succinate) on Chromosorb-W (60-80 mesh), in an A-350B Aerograph instrument or on Column SE-30, 10% Silicone Rubber on 80-100 S, in an F and M. Lab Gas Chromatograph Model 700. I.r. spectra are recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 21B Double Beam Spectrometer. N.m.r. spectra are registered in a 100 MHz spectrometer using solutions in CDCl_3 , C_6D_6 or CCl_4 as specified with tetramethylsilane as an internal standard; the chemical shifts (δ) are given in p.p.m.

Sylveterpineol : *d*-Sylvestrene dihydrochloride [m.p. 72-73°, (α) $_D^{30}$ +19.4° (*c* 1.0)] (10 g.) was mixed with two per cent aqueous potassium hydroxide (500 ml.) in a 1-litre round bottom flask fitted with a Liebig condenser and stirred vigorously (magnetic) for 5 hr. at 70-75°. The reaction mixture was distilled in a current of steam and the volatile oil obtained was repeatedly washed with water. If the oil was not free from chlorine, the treatment with alkali was carried out once again. The reaction was repeated several times to obtain \sim 90-95 g. of oil, b.p. 50-95°/5 mm., d_{25}^{25} 0.9230, (α) $_D^{20}$ +47.82° (*c* 1.1), n_D^{25} 1.4694.

On precise fractionation, this oil afforded a cut (59.92%), b.p. 90-92°/5 mm., d_{25}^{25} 0.9310, (α) $_D^{25}$ +46.70° (*c* 1.0), n_D^{20} 1.4821 (Found : C, 78.29; H, 11.63. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{OH}$ requires C, 77.87; H, 11.76%), t.l.c.: 2 spots (R_f 0.52 and 0.60), g.l.c.: 2 peaks (area ratio 7 : 13 in the order of elution).

Esterification : The above alcohol (37.3 g.) in anhydrous pyridine (80 ml.) was treated with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (50 g.) in small portions with vigorous stirring, precautions being taken to maintain the reaction mixture below 60°. After keeping for ten days at room temperature (\sim 30°), it was extracted with ether (800 ml.). The ether extract was successively washed with 5% hydrochloric acid (3 \times 25 ml.), 5% sodium bicarbonate solution (5 \times 25 ml.) and with water and dried. The expulsion of the solvent resulted in a dark brown sticky liquid (73 g.) which on trituration with absolute ethanol (10 ml.) completely solidified to a pale yellow hard mass. This was broken up into small bits and dried for 2 days on sheets of filter paper (72 g.), m.p. 45-50°.

The crude ester was dissolved in hot ethanol (500 ml.), filtered and the filtrate allowed to cool. The crystals obtained were filtered off and dried (37.5 g.), m.p. 65-68°. This was subjected to fivefold recrystallisation from ethanol (17.5 g.), m.p. 98°, (α) $_D^{20}$ +54.85° (*c* 1.2) (Found : C, 67.34; H, 7.17; N, 5.15%. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{N}$: requires C, 67.26; H, 6.99; N, 4.62%). I.r. and n.m.r. spectra as described above.

Saponification : A solution of the ester (10 g.) in ether (\sim 250 ml.) was heated under reflux at 60-70° with a solution of potassium hydroxide (7 g.) in methanol (70 ml.). Usual work up afforded an oil and this was taken up in petroleum ether (100 ml.) and washed with distilled water (3 \times 25 ml.). The organic phase was separated, dried and expulsion of the solvent furnished a colourless oil which on steam distillation followed by distillation in vacuo afforded a pleasant smelling oil (3.1 g.), b.p. 91°/5 mm., d_{25}^{25} 0.9380, (α) $_D^{25}$ +102.8° (*c* 1.3), n_D^{20}

1-4830 (Found : C, 77.95; H, 11.50%. $C_{10}H_{17}OH$ requires C, 77.87; H, 11.76%), t.l.c.: single spot (R_f 0.51), g.l.c.: single peak, i.r. and n.m.r. spectra as described earlier.

Oxidation : To a stirred solution of potassium permanganate (10 g.) in water (400 ml.), chilled in ice-bath, was added the alcohol (10 g.) in small portions during the course of 1 hr. After the addition of alcohol, stirring was continued for further 2 hr. at ice-bath temperature. The manganese dioxide sludge was filtered off under suction and then leached with boiling water (8×50 ml.). From the filtrate and washings (800 ml.) the unreacted alcohol (~ 1.8 g.) was extracted by shaking with petroleum ether (25 ml.). Evaporated the aqueous layer to dryness on a boiling water-bath under carbon dioxide atmosphere. The residue was extracted with absolute ethanol (60 ml.); the expulsion of the solvent followed by distillation in vacuo provided a cut (5.5 g.), b.p. $167-168^\circ/11$ mm. The distillate was taken up in ethyl acetate (12 ml.) and regenerated by addition of petroleum ether (12 ml.) and cooling. This gave a colourless syrupy liquid (4.0 g.), b.p. $167-168^\circ/11$ mm., $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 23.66^\circ$ (c 1.1); t.l.c.: single spot (R_f 0.58) [solvent : *n*-butanol-water (9 : 1); spray reagent : chromic acid-sulphuric acid] (Found : C, 62.30; H, 10.68%. $C_{10}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 63.79; H, 10.71%). N.m.r. data as described above.

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